

>> WHO ARE THE PARTNERS IN COLOVOC?

- **Metabolomics Platform,**
Institut d'Investigació Pere Virgili
(IISPV), Spain

- **Fiehn Laboratory,**
University of California Davis (UC
Davis), USA

- **Biosfer Teslab SL,** Reus, Spain

>> KEY DATA

Start date: 1st July 2019
Runtime: 3 years
Structure: 9 Work packages
EC funding: 257,191.20€

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme Under Grant Agreement no. 798038.

COLOVOC

**Reliable and specific
urinary biomarkers for
colorectal cancer**

<http://www.iispv.cat/recerca/research-groups/13/plataforma-metabolomica>

>> WHAT IS COLOVOC ABOUT?

People with Fecal Immunochemical Test POSITIVE

Metabolomics

Reproducibility within laboratories

Multivariate statistical analysis

Metabolic pathways and mapping

>> OBJECTIVES OF COLOVOC?

The main aim of this project is to identify new biomarkers and/or validate proposed ones and to explore colorectal cancer diagnosis

Use of metabolomic tools for the early diagnosis of colorectal cancer (CRC).

Colorectal Cancer Biomarkers

Polyps Biomarkers

Healthy Biomarkers

Samples of people that will undergo a colonoscopy (before bowel cleaning diet).

We aim to develop a diagnostics prototype test for CRC.

>> METABOLOMICS

We study the metabolome. The result products of our biological systems.

GENOMICS
WHAT CAN HAPPEN

TRANSCRIPTOMICS
WHAT APPEARS TO BE HAPPENING

proteins

PROTEOMICS
WHAT MAKES THINGS HAPPEN

Metabolites

METABOLOMICS
WHAT IS HAPPENING NOW